

Development of Veterinary Inhalation Anaesthesia in Large Animals: A Historical and Technical Analysis of Królikowski's 1890 Intratracheal Device

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a documented analysis and technical reconstruction of a veterinary chloroform inhalation device described in Polish scientific literature in 1890. The introduction of inhalation anaesthesia with ether, nitrous oxide, and chloroform in human medicine substantially changed surgical practice, and these methods were subsequently adopted and adapted for veterinary use. In 1890, Professor Stanisław Królikowski published a report in *Przegląd Weterynarski* describing an apparatus designed for inhalation anaesthesia in horses and other large animals. Unlike devices adapted from human medicine, this instrument enabled direct intratracheal administration of chloroform vapour, with the aim of shortening induction time, reducing drug consumption, and improving practical use under field conditions. Based on historical source analysis and comparison with nineteenth-century veterinary anaesthetic equipment, this study reconstructs the structure, function, and clinical rationale of the device and places it within the broader development of large-animal anaesthesia in Central Europe.

Keywords: veterinary anaesthesia; chloroform; intratracheal anaesthesia; history of veterinary medicine; veterinary history; Królikowski

INTRODUCTION

Pain associated with surgical procedures has been a central concern of surgery since antiquity. Efforts to alleviate it long predate the emergence of modern anaesthesiology. Already in the Middle Ages, attempts were made to induce sleep and reduce pain using pharmacological preparations. One of the earliest documented examples is the *spongia somnifera* described by the Dominican friar Theodoric Borgognoni—a sponge soaked in plant-derived sedative substances. Although such preparations represent

early attempts at controlled anaesthesia, they gradually fell out of use [1,2]. A similar trajectory can be observed in the case of Paracelsus, who described the narcotic effects of ether in animals in the early seventeenth century; these observations, however, were not translated into clinical practice [3,4]. In the first half of the nineteenth century, both pharmacological and physical approaches to pain control were explored. In 1824, Henry Hickman experimented with carbon dioxide to induce narcosis in animals and demonstrated that minor surgical procedures could be performed under its inhalation. However, the toxicity of the gas and the difficulty of controlling its effects prevented wider adoption [5]. Physical methods were also investigated. John Hunter and Dominique Jean Larrey examined nerve compression as a means of local anaesthesia, while Larrey observed that cooling tissues before amputation reduced pain perception, anticipating later developments in cryotherapy. James Arnott subsequently expanded these observations, introducing cooling techniques into surgical and trauma practice using a spray composed of ice and salt [6,7]. A decisive turning point came with the introduction of inhalation anaesthetics. In 1799, Humphry Davy described the analgesic and narcotic effects of nitrous oxide in both animals and humans and suggested its possible surgical application, although this proposal was not immediately adopted [8]. Modern anaesthesiology is commonly dated to the public demonstration of ether anaesthesia by William T. G. Morton in Boston in 1846, which transformed operative practice [3]. Shortly thereafter, James Young Simpson introduced chloroform into clinical use. In 1847, he employed it as an anaesthetic following preliminary trials that included experiments on animals. Physiological studies by Jean Pierre Flourens confirmed its ability to induce controlled narcosis [9–11]. These developments were rapidly transferred to veterinary medicine. As early as 1847, M. F. Defays used ether to anaesthetise horses, constructing a dedicated mask and publishing both the apparatus and the method. One year later, Thiernes reported experimental administration of chloroform in dogs, analysing dosage and physiological responses [12,13]. In Vienna, on 27 January 1847, Professor Franz Schuh performed one of the first public demonstrations of ether anaesthesia in a human patient at the Allgemeines Krankenhaus. At approximately the same time, the veterinarian Joseph Seifert, court veterinary surgeon to Emperor Franz Joseph, initiated experiments with ether in domestic animals. These trials culminated in a series of public demonstrations on 6, 8, and 9 February 1847 involving horses, cattle, goats, and dogs, using a nasal inhalation apparatus specifically constructed for large animals rather than adapted from human surgical equipment [14]. Despite these advances, suitable equipment for large animals remained limited. Most surgical procedures in horses and cattle continued to be performed on conscious animals using restraint or casting techniques, which carried a high risk of injury and complications for both animals and operators [15]. By the second half of the nineteenth century, the main obstacle to the wider use of anaesthesia in veterinary practice was therefore not pharmacological but technical. Devices designed for human patients proved inadequate in terms of sealing, capacity, and dosage control when

applied to large animals, particularly under field conditions. This created a clear need for instruments designed specifically for veterinary use.

Within this context, the publication by Stanisław Królikowski is of particular importance. On 1 December 1890, he published an article in *Przegląd Weterynarski* describing a “device for the anaesthesia of animals by introducing chloroform into the trachea.” In this work, Królikowski presented an apparatus intended for general anaesthesia in large animals, designed from the outset to meet the anatomical and practical requirements of veterinary surgery rather than relying on adaptations of human medical equipment. Despite its relevance, the device has received little attention in modern historiography and has not been systematically analysed in the context of the development of veterinary anaesthetic technology [16–18].

The aim of the present study is to reconstruct the structure and operating principles of Królikowski’s apparatus, to analyse its historical and clinical context, and to assess its place in the broader development of veterinary anaesthesia and specialised technologies for large animals. This article focuses on the technical and clinical aspects of the intratracheal device and does not attempt to provide a comprehensive account of nineteenth-century anaesthetic pharmacology.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study employs a historical–analytical research design based on primary archival veterinary sources. The principal material consists of the original Polish-language article by Stanisław Królikowski, published in 1890 in *Przegląd Weterynarski* (Vol. 5, No. 12, pp. 268–273) [16], in which the author described the construction and use of an intratracheal chloroform inhalation device intended for large animals. The original document was examined in its archival form and translated into English for the purposes of technical and clinical interpretation. A qualitative content analysis was conducted to extract detailed information concerning the design of the apparatus, including its dimensions, materials, structural components, and operating principles. Particular attention was given to descriptions of the reservoir, tubing system, compression bulb, and tracheal needle, which were interpreted in terms of their probable mechanical and functional roles as presented in the original text. To situate the invention within its broader medical context, a comparative historical analysis was performed. Nineteenth-century human and veterinary inhalation anaesthesia devices described in surgical manuals, historical monographs, and veterinary literature were reviewed and compared with Królikowski’s design. This approach allowed assessment of similarities, differences, and potential innovations in relation to mask-based and reservoir systems commonly used at the time. Secondary sources were consulted to evaluate the clinical and technological significance of the device within the development of large-animal anaesthesia and early airway management techniques. As the study is based exclusively on archival documents

and published historical materials, it does not involve live animals or human subjects; therefore, ethical approval was not required.

RESULTS

The author emphasised that the inhalation devices available at the time were complicated, fragile, bulky, heavy, and expensive, which limited their practical use in veterinary medicine [16]. A further problem was that animals were often required to remain standing during anaesthesia; once unconscious, they could collapse and sustain fractures. For this reason, chloroform administration in a recumbent position was considered preferable. Królikowski first discussed Reisser's inhalation barrel, a device composed of pipes, masks, and a leather bag, measuring approximately one metre in height. Its construction proved problematic in practice: the tin elements were prone to bending, the barrel could open unintentionally, the spring mechanism corroded easily, and the leather bag tended to dry out and rupture. In addition, the apparatus required relatively large quantities of chloroform. The second device described was William's cone apparatus, which, according to Królikowski, was only slightly smaller than Reisser's barrel. Its use required a special hanger, resembling a bridle, used to secure the apparatus to the animal's mouth. This element appeared to be specific to this device and did not correspond clearly to other categories of veterinary equipment. The third device, the Defays apparatus, was described as being "rarely used nowadays." Its components, including the valve and a wire tube covered with leather, were easily damaged. The apparatus consisted of a wire frame covered with gutta-percha cloth, forming a basket-like muzzle placed over the horse's nose and mouth. The journal editors added a footnote explaining that gutta-percha resin was obtained from the sap of gutta-percha trees and was widely used in dentistry. Królikowski noted that the original wire-and-leather tube had been replaced with a thick rubber tube approximately 1.5 m in length. Despite this modification, the device remained expensive, and its rubber components deteriorated rapidly, particularly under the influence of chloroform vapours. Another method described was the Raux apparatus from Toulon, whose main element was a pig's bladder tied around the horse's muzzle, resembling a simple drawstring bag. A similar solution was proposed by Peuch of Lyon, consisting of a leather feeding muzzle into which several chloroform-soaked tampons were inserted. Openings at the back and sides allowed air to enter. Although these devices were mechanically simpler, Królikowski observed that they did not provide an adequate supply of fresh air, as inhaled and exhaled air mixed within the enclosure. He further noted that he had not encountered their use in practice. The final method discussed was that recommended by Bouley, which dispensed with any apparatus. In this approach, two chloroform-soaked sponges were inserted into the animal's nostrils, with additional chloroform applied periodically. Królikowski criticised this method for restricting respiration, limiting air supply, and causing inflammation of the nasal mucosa, accompanied by several days of nasal discharge, although without severe complications.

He concluded that this technique also failed to gain wider acceptance. Following this review, Królikowski proposed a different approach based on direct intratracheal administration of chloroform. He formulated four design assumptions for the device:

- (1) it should be compact, durable, and easy to transport;
- (2) it should allow anaesthesia of animals in both standing and recumbent positions, regardless of size or species;
- (3) it should minimise the time required to achieve general anaesthesia;
- (4) it should reduce chloroform consumption as far as possible.

The apparatus consisted of:

- a thick glass bottle with a graduated scale (10 g of chloroform), sufficiently heavy to stand independently;
- a tube connecting the bottle to a balloon, equipped with a movable elbow joint;
- a red rubber balloon approximately 7 cm in length;
- a second tube attached to the balloon outlet;
- injection needles in three sizes, each with a pyramid-shaped tip and a rubber disc on the shaft to limit penetration depth and prevent damage to the tracheal wall.

The device weighed approximately 420 g and measured 30 cm in height.

In his concluding remarks, Królikowski stated that the apparatus was:

- (1) small, durable, and portable;
- (2) suitable for anaesthetising large animals regardless of head shape;
- (3) efficient in terms of both time and chloroform consumption;
- (4) inexpensive, with a unit cost of 8 złotych, supplied by a manufacturer identified as Preyer.

The original publication was accompanied by a single illustration of the device (Fig. 1) and did not include a reference list.

Figure 1. Original illustration of Królikowski's intratracheal chloroform device (*Przegląd Weterynarski*, 1890), showing the overall structure of the apparatus.

DISCUSSION

Until the late nineteenth century, most surgical procedures in horses were performed without general anaesthesia. Animals were operated on either in a standing position or after being forcibly cast to the ground using ropes. Contemporary veterinary authors increasingly criticised these practices, pointing not only to the high rate of complications but also to the ethical implications of operating on conscious, struggling animals. From a modern perspective, such methods raise serious animal welfare concerns and underscore the need for safe and effective anaesthetic techniques in large animals. Contemporary veterinary manuals indicate that surgical procedures in horses were commonly performed in standing animals or after casting, often resulting in severe complications for both animals and operators [16]. Attempts to introduce inhalation anaesthesia into equine practice during the nineteenth century were limited largely by the absence of appropriate equipment. Chloroform masks and inhalers designed for human surgery proved unsuitable, as they did not allow reliable control of dosage and were poorly adapted to equine anatomy. Merillat emphasised that such devices were impractical: animals resisted the mask or suffocated, dosage remained unpredictable, and the risk of fatal collapse was considerable [16]. Earlier efforts had already been made in Central

Europe. In 1847, Joseph Seifert in Vienna conducted public demonstrations of ether anaesthesia in horses using a purpose-built nasal inhalation apparatus designed specifically for large animals rather than adapted from human equipment. These experiments represent one of the earliest documented applications of inhalation anaesthesia in veterinary practice and demonstrate that the search for species-specific technical solutions had begun several decades earlier [14]. These observations point to a well-recognised clinical and practical problem: the absence of a safe, repeatable, and controllable method of general anaesthesia in large animals. It was this need—rather than purely theoretical interest—that underpinned the device proposed by Stanisław Królikowski in 1890. His approach sought to overcome the limitations of nasal administration of volatile anaesthetics by delivering chloroform vapour directly into the trachea, a method he termed *pulverisatio intratrachealis* [16]. The apparatus consisted of a glass reservoir for liquid chloroform, a rubber compression bulb to generate pressure, and a metal tube ending in a trocar-like needle, the diameter of which could be adjusted according to species. According to Królikowski, full surgical anaesthesia in a horse could be achieved within approximately eight minutes using 20–80 g of chloroform, providing up to thirty minutes of operative time without additional dosing. In contrast to the complex inhalation systems used in human surgery, the device was deliberately simple: portable, relatively inexpensive, and adaptable to different species through modification of the needle and tubing. It was conceived as a practical field instrument for military, agricultural, and rural settings, where access to specialised facilities was limited. No physical specimen of the apparatus has survived. Its existence is documented solely in the original 1890 publication in *Przeгляд Weterynarski*, accompanied by a single woodcut illustration. From a modern perspective, the device may be interpreted as an early attempt at direct airway management in large animals. Although intratracheal administration of chloroform would not meet current safety standards, the underlying concept anticipates several principles central to modern veterinary anaesthesia, including direct airway access, rapid induction, reduction of anatomical dead space, and equipment portability. These features parallel contemporary endotracheal intubation and mobile inhalation systems used in equine practice. In this sense, the apparatus represents more than a historical curiosity and may be regarded as an early conceptual precursor of modern airway management techniques in large animals. The invention must also be considered within its institutional and political context. The Imperial and Royal School of Veterinary Medicine in Lviv, founded in 1881, was the first Polish-language veterinary academy in the Austro-Hungarian Empire and formed part of a centrally organised system of veterinary education. Its curriculum reflected the priorities of the Habsburg administration, which regarded veterinary medicine not only as an academic discipline but also as a component of military and agricultural policy, particularly in relation to horses used in artillery, transport, and cavalry [17]. The school maintained extensive clinical facilities for large animals, including an operating theatre and dedicated areas for training in restraint

techniques [16]. In such an environment, the absence of reliable anaesthesia constituted a daily clinical limitation rather than an abstract problem. Stanisław Królikowski, appointed professor of anatomy and surgery in 1886 and later rector of the institution, published extensively on equine surgery and restraint methods [18]. His 1890 apparatus should therefore be interpreted not as an isolated experiment but as a direct response to a clearly recognised clinical need within one of the busiest equine hospitals of the late Habsburg monarchy. This example illustrates that progress in veterinary anaesthesia during the nineteenth century depended not only on pharmacological advances but also on practical engineering solutions adapted to the anatomical and logistical realities of large-animal practice. Królikowski's design thus represents an early instance of veterinary-specific anaesthetic technology developed independently of human surgical equipment. Despite its conceptual originality, several factors likely limited its adoption. By the 1890s, chloroform—the agent for which the device was designed—was increasingly criticised in both human and veterinary medicine because of its narrow safety margin and risk of sudden cardiac arrest [4, 10]. Many contemporary manuals recommended ether as a safer alternative for large animals [16]. The technique itself required invasive puncture of the trachea, demanding surgical skill and aseptic conditions that were difficult to achieve in field settings. In addition, veterinary instrument manufacture was still poorly developed, and the device was neither patented nor commercially produced. As a result, it remained a local innovation rather than becoming part of standard practice. Its disappearance was further reinforced by historical discontinuity. Political upheavals, institutional changes, and the eventual dissolution of the Lviv veterinary school disrupted the transmission of local surgical knowledge and innovations [18]. In contrast to British and American centres, where stronger archival continuity facilitated the preservation of technical developments, many Central European contributions were not incorporated into later textbooks or teaching traditions.

This study has several limitations. No physical specimens of the apparatus have survived, and its reconstruction is based entirely on archival descriptions and a single historical illustration. Some technical aspects therefore remain interpretative. Nevertheless, the available evidence allows a plausible reconstruction of the device and supports its interpretation within the early development of veterinary anaesthesia.

CONCLUSIONS

The fate of Królikowski's device illustrates not only the limited uptake of a single invention, but also the broader marginalisation of non-Anglophone and non-industrial centres of veterinary innovation within the global narrative of anaesthesiology. Only recent scholarship has begun to address this gap [18]. Professor Stanisław Królikowski's 1890 article represents the earliest identified Polish-language publication devoted to the technical design of a device for general inhalation anaesthesia in large animals and marks an early stage in the development of veterinary anaesthesiology in Central Europe. His

intratracheal chloroform apparatus offered a lightweight and portable alternative to the heavy and fragile inhalation devices then used in equine practice, with the aim of shortening induction time and reducing chloroform consumption. Although the instrument does not appear to have achieved wider clinical adoption, the publication itself reflects a transition in veterinary surgery—from reliance on modified human medical equipment towards the development of purpose-built veterinary technologies. The device illustrates how nineteenth-century innovation in veterinary medicine was shaped not only by pharmacological advances but also by practical responses to anatomical, logistical, and economic constraints specific to large-animal practice. It may therefore be regarded as a case study in the material and procedural history of veterinary anaesthesia and as an early example of technical innovation in Polish veterinary literature.

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